

The Effect of Work Motivation, Work Discipline, Compensation, And Work Facilities on Employee Performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua

Ni Putu Ayu Dyah Tamara Cancera Arta¹, Putu Ngurah Suyatna Yasa², Ida Bagus Agung Dharmanegara³

^{1,2,3} Master of Management Study Program, Postgraduate Faculty, Warmadewa University

Article DOI: [10.55677/SSHBR/2025-3050-0405](https://doi.org/10.55677/SSHBR/2025-3050-0405)

DOI URL: <https://doi.org/10.55677/SSHBR/2025-3050-0405>

KEYWORDS: work motivation, discipline, compensation, facilities, employee performance.

ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the effects of work motivation, work discipline, compensation, and work facilities on employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa, located on Jalan Taman Giri, Nusa Dua. The research method employed is quantitative, based on a sample of 31 employees collected using saturated sampling techniques. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using *Structural Equation Modeling* (SEM) based on *Partial Least Squares* (PLS). The results showed that work motivation, work discipline, compensation, and work facilities have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Work motivation has the highest path coefficient (0.430), followed by work discipline (0.578), compensation (0.182), and work facilities (0.097). These findings indicate that increasing these four factors can drive employee performance optimally. This study provides practical implications for management to pay attention to these aspects in an effort to improve employee performance and service quality at Galaxy Salon and Spa.

Corresponding Author:

Ni Putu Ayu Dyah Tamara Cancera Arta

Published:

April 12, 2025

License:

This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

INTRODUCTION

Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua is one of the leading beauty salons in Bali Province, especially in the Nusa Dua area of South Kuta District, which offers various beauty and spa treatments tailored to customer needs. Although Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua is known as one of the reputable salons and spas in Nusa Dua, several customer reviews on *Google Reviews* still show indications of a decline in the quality of employee performance (Rohendi, 2016). Several customers complained about the slow service provided by employees, the incompatibility of the products used, and prices that did not match the service received by customers. These indications indicate the need for a more in-depth evaluation of employee performance to ensure that the services provided continue to meet the standards expected by customers (Praditya, 2022).

Based on the observation results, it can also be seen that work discipline is still a challenge faced by Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua. Some employees often arrive late, are absent without notice, or pay less attention to punctuality in providing services to customers. Lack of discipline in work can reduce the quality of service provided, thus negatively impacting overall customer satisfaction (Merli et al., 2019; Saputra, Laksmi, et al., 2024; Zhu et al., 2023).

Some employees feel that the salary and incentives they receive are not in accordance with the workload they have to bear. Employees who feel their compensation is inadequate tend to show lower levels of job satisfaction, have decreased work motivation, and tend to look for other job opportunities (Anggreni et al., 2023; Juniariani & Saputra, 2020). There is several equipment used in the service that are no longer in optimal condition, a lack of maintenance supplies, and a lack of rest space for employees. This condition can have an impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of employee work, where employees cannot work optimally due to limited facilities provided (Saputra et al., 2023). In addition, the lack of adequate facilities can also affect work comfort and employee satisfaction in carrying out their duties. (Sujana & Saputra, 2020).

Based on the results of this observation, it can be concluded that factors such as work motivation, work discipline, compensation, and work facilities have an important role in determining employee performance. Therefore, an appropriate strategy is needed to improve these four aspects to ensure that employee performance remains optimal and can provide the best service to customers. Success in maintaining a business's reputation and competitiveness cannot be separated from the important role of

employee performance. Therefore, identifying and understanding the factors that influence employee performance is crucial to ensure that salon operations run optimally and provide maximum satisfaction to customers (Yin et al., 2019).

The importance of employee performance in achieving the success of a business so that it is important to conduct a study on what factors can affect employee performance. Considering the problem of employee performance at Galaxy Salon Dan Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua which is indicated by the lack of appreciation, low employee work discipline, employee dissatisfaction with compensation, and limited facilities that can hinder employee work effectiveness, as well as the inconsistency of previous research results, the current study is being conducted again related to the study of employee performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance Theory

Gibson (1987) introduced a performance theory that explains how individual behavior affects their performance. In this theory, Gibson presents a model and analyzes several factors that affect individual behavior and performance. There are three categories of variables in this performance theory, namely individual variables, psychological variables, and organizational variables (Hanif et al., 2012). Individual variables can be divided into sub-variables of abilities and skills, background, and demographic characteristics. Meanwhile, psychological variables consist of sub-variables such as perception, attitude, personality, learning, and motivation. Meanwhile, organizational variables are included in sub-variables such as resources, leadership, rewards, organizational structure, and job design.

Goal Setting Theory

This study uses *Goal Setting Theory* as the main theory (*grand theory*). *Goal Setting Theory* is a form of motivation theory (Abdou et al., 2020). *Goal Setting Theory* emphasizes the importance of the relationship between the goals set and the performance produced. The basic concept is that someone who is able to understand the goals expected by the organization, then that understanding will affect their work behavior. *Goal Setting Theory* suggests that an individual is committed to the goal (Taylor, 2019).

Employee performance

Performance in an organization is the answer to the success or failure of the organization's goals that have been set. An organization is always driven by a group of people who play an active role in achieving the goals that the organization wants to achieve. The organization's goals will certainly not be achieved if the performance of its employees is not optimal. Muisyo et al. (2022) explains that employee performance refers to the level of fulfillment of tasks that form the employee's job. According to Mondy (2019) states that performance management is a goal-oriented process that is directed at ensuring that organizational processes are in place to maximize the productivity of employees, teams, and ultimately the company organization.

Work motivation

Martela et al. (2021) stated that motivation is the provision of driving force that creates a person's passion for work so that they are able to work together, work effectively, and with integrity, with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. Saputra (2019) stated that work motivation is a drive within a person to do their work with real enthusiasm and full responsibility. Motivation is a person's drive to do a job so that employees can achieve their goals (Sari et al., 2023). Strong motivation makes employees excited to work so that employee performance increases, Motivation can come from internal or external sources.

Work Discipline

Work discipline is a tool used by managers to change behavior and as an effort to increase awareness and willingness of a person to obey all company regulations and applicable social norms (Nurhuda et al., 2019). According to Siswanto (2020), work discipline is an attitude of respecting, appreciating, obeying, and complying with applicable regulations, both written and unwritten, and being able to carry them out and not avoiding sanctions if they violate the duties and authorities given.

Compensation

According to Dessler (2017:221), compensation is something in the form of payment to be given to employees and things related to employees. Then, according to Sedarmayanti (2019:263) compensation is everything that employees will receive as a form of compensation for employee work. Compensation is a part of a reward or award that is only related to the economic part, but after the belief that individual behavior is influenced by a broader spectrum system, compensation cannot be separated from the rewards provided by the organization (Sara et al., 2021). Sinambela (2016) also stated that compensation is the sum of all gifts given by the organization to employees in return for their services.

Work Facilities

Work facilities are supporting facilities in the company's activities in physical form, and are used in the company's normal activities, have a relatively permanent useful life, and provide benefits for the future. According to Ragil Anandita et al., (2021), Facilities are something that is used, worn, occupied, and enjoyed by employees in direct relation to work or for the smooth running of work. "Work facilities are a means provided by the company to support the running of the company's business in achieving the

goals set by the control holder (Apri Dahlius & Ibrahim, 2016) ". Bohdanowicz and Martina (2007) argue, "Facilities can be interpreted as anything that can facilitate and expedite the implementation of all efforts". Based on the above understanding, it can be concluded that facilities are a means to facilitate and facilitate the implementation of functions. The involvement of librarians and administrative staff is very important in determining the procurement of these college library facilities, so that the availability of library collections becomes meaningful because of the support of well-designed facilities.

Hypothesis Formulation

Motivation to work determines the high or low performance produced by an employee. Employees who have high work motivation tend to have higher work enthusiasm so that they will be encouraged to work harder and ultimately produce more optimal performance (Wang et al., 2021) . The higher the employee's motivation to work tends to lead to an increase in the performance produced. Research conducted by Sriyani *et al.*, (2023) found that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance where employees with high work motivation produce more optimal performance. In line with the results of this study, research conducted by Antika *et al.*, (2021); Rulianti *et al.*, (2021); Goni *et al.*, (2021); and Guterres *et al.*, (2019) also found that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This indicates that employees who have high work enthusiasm tend to be motivated to work optimally so that they can achieve optimal performance. Based on this description, the hypotheses formulated in this study are:

H₁ : Work motivation has a positive and significant influence on employee performance.

Research conducted by Nabilla *et al.*, (2024) found that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. In line with the results of this study, research conducted by Arisanti (2019); Sazly & Winna (2019); Luddin & Supriyati (2018); Sunarni *et al.*, (2024); and Nurzakiah & Febrian (2024) found that work discipline has a significant positive effect on employee performance. This indicates that employees with high work discipline tend to produce better performance. Based on this description, the hypotheses formulated in this study are:

H₂ : Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Research conducted by Nursella *et al.*, (2025) found that compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, where the better the compensation given to employees tends to increase employee performance achievements. In line with these results, research conducted by Yuningsih *et al.*, (2020); Rahmadani *et al.*, (2023); Nurzakiah & Febrian (2024); and Milen *et al.*, (2025) also found that compensation has a significant positive effect on employee performance. This indicates that employees tend to provide optimal performance by providing fair and good compensation to employees. Based on this description, the hypotheses formulated in this study are:

H₃ : Compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Research conducted by Pratiwi (2019) stated that work facilities have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, where the more adequate the work facilities are, the more employee performance will increase. In line with these results, research conducted by Sari & Puspita (2023); Nurhadian (2021); Monalisa *et al.*, (2022); and Anandita *et al.*, (2021) found that work facilities have a significant positive effect on employee performance. This indicates that the provision of good work facilities can improve employee performance optimally. Based on this description, the hypotheses formulated in this study are:

H₄ : Work facilities have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

METHOD

This research is a quantitative associative research. This study aims to explain the influence of work motivation variables, work discipline, compensation, and work facilities on employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua. The variables in this study will be described in indicators that are in accordance with the appropriate measurements for each variable. These variables are obtained through theoretical and empirical studies from previous studies. Through these studies, the formulation of the problem and research hypothesis are obtained. Before conducting statistical data testing, the research sample, type of data, and data source must be determined first. The hypothesis is tested using Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. After the research results are obtained, the results are interpreted to answer the formulation of the problem in this study so that a research conclusion can be obtained. (Harris et al., 2021) .

The type of data used in this study is quantitative data. The population in this study were all employees at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua, totaling 31 employees . The determination of the sample in this study used a saturated sampling technique. This technique is usually applied if the population is relatively small or the study wants to cover all elements of the population without selecting a specific sample. Based on this, the number of samples used in this study was 31 employees of Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua. The questionnaire distributed was in the form of a list of written statements to respondents regarding work motivation, work discipline, compensation, work facilities, and employee performance. The list of statements with a *Likert scale option* with an interval of 7 (seven) levels where respondents were given the freedom to determine their opinions or opinions on the questionnaire. The research instrument needs to be tested to determine the validity of the data and the reliability of the data used, so that validity testing and reliability testing are carried out. The measurement model or *Outer Model* is used to test the validity and reliability of a construct or research instrument. Conclusions are drawn based on information obtained from samples

in the population. The inferential statistical tool used in this study is *Structural Equation Modeling* with *Partial Least Square*. using *SmartPLS* software version 3. *PLS* is one of the *Structural Problem Solving Methods Equation Modeling (SEM)* which in this case is more compared to other *SEM* techniques .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Respondent characteristics show the identity of the respondents used in this study. Respondents in this study have different characteristics or identities in filling out the questionnaire.

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

No.	Respondent Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	By Gender		
	Man	8	25.81
	Woman	23	74.19
	Amount	31	100
2	By Age		
	21 – 25 years	7	22.58
	26 – 30 years	13	41.94
	31 – 35 years	4	12.90
	36 – 40 years	5	16.13
	> 40 years	2	6.45
	Amount	31	100
3	By Position		
	Hair Stylist	17	54.84
	Spa Therapist	5	16.13
	Manicurist/Pedicurist	4	12.90
	Receptionist	2	6.45
	Cleaning Services	3	9.68
	Amount	31	100
4	Based on Last Education		
	Vocational High School	13	41.94
	Diploma	11	35.48
	Bachelor	7	22.58
	Amount	31	100

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that the characteristics of the respondents used in this study are based on gender, age, position, and last education. Table 1 also shows that the majority in this study were female salon employees, which shows that work in the beauty services sector is still dominated by female workers. This is in line with gender stereotypes in society that associate skills and interests in the beauty sector more with women. In terms of age, most respondents are in the 26-30 year age range, which is included in the productive age category and is active in the world of work. This age range also indicates that the respondents have sufficient work experience and are stable in carrying out their profession. Meanwhile, the majority of respondents have positions as *hair stylists* , which are positions that play a direct role in providing primary services in salons. This shows that this study targets core workers who have technical skills and interact directly with customers. In terms of education, most respondents have a final education of SMK/STM, which generally focuses on vocational or vocational education. This shows that the workforce in salons comes from many practical skills-based education, in accordance with the needs of the beauty services industry which prioritizes technical skills over formal academic education.

Descriptive statistical analysis is used to describe or explain data on research variables based on the number of samples, average value (mean), standard deviation, maximum value, and minimum value.

Table 2. Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis

	N	Min.	max.	Mean	Std. Deviation
Work Motivation (X_1)	31	17	35	31.71	3,761
Work Discipline (X_2)	31	20	35	31.90	3,727

Compensation (X ₃)	31	20	35	31.65	3.656
Work Facilities (Z)	31	20	35	30.45	4.836
Employee Performance (Y)	31	21	42	38.16	4,525

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2025

Measurement Model or *Outer Model* is used to describe the relationship between latent variables/constructs with each indicator block (Hair *et al.*, 2013). This measurement model is used to test the validity and reliability of the construct of the research instrument. The results of the convergent validity test using *outer loading* show that Each indicator used in this study has a value greater than 0.7 so that the data has met convergent validity. The *cross loading value* indicates the existence of discriminant validity, good, where this can be seen from the correlation value of the indicator to its construct is higher than the correlation value of the indicator with other constructs. Reliability testing is applied to measure the consistency, accuracy and precision of measuring instruments in measuring a concept and can be used to measure the consistency of respondents in answering question items in a questionnaire. Each *Cronbach's Alpha* and *Composite Reliability value* for each research construct obtained a value greater than 0.7 so that it can be concluded that all constructs/latent variables in this study are reliable. After conducting an evaluation of the Measurement Model (*Outer Model*), a Structural Model Evaluation (*Inner Model*) was carried out using *Bootstrapping*. Structural Model is a model used to test the relationship between previously hypothesized latent constructs/variables. *The Inner Model* in PLS is evaluated by looking at the *R-squared value (R²)* or coefficient of determination and the t-value or path coefficient value (Hair, *et.al* 2013).

It can be seen that the coefficient of determination (*R-square*) value of the employee performance variable is 0.960, which means that 96 percent of the employee performance variable influenced by variables of work motivation, work discipline, compensation, and work facilities while 4 percent are influenced by other variables not used in this study. The path coefficient value (t-value) is used to test the significance of a construct or latent variable through the estimation of the path coefficient value (t-value) obtained by the *bootstrapping procedure* with a value considered significant if the p-value ≤ 0.05 . The test results are presented in the following table:

Table 3. Path Coefficient

Hypothesis	Variable Relationship	Original Sample (O)	P Values	Information
H ₁	Work Motivation (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.430	0,000	H ₁ accepted
H ₂	Work Discipline (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.578	0,000	H ₂ accepted
H ₃	Compensation (X3) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.182	0.034	H ₃ accepted
H ₄	Work Facilities (X4) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.097	0.011	H ₄ accepted

Source: Processed primary data, 2025

The first hypothesis (H₁) in this study states that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Based on Table 5.14, it can be seen that the path coefficient value obtained has a positive value, namely 0.430 with *p-values* = 0.000 < 0.05 so that H₁ is accepted. This shows that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua. The second hypothesis (H₂) in this study states that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Based on Table 5.14, it can be seen that the path coefficient value obtained has a positive value, namely 0.578 with *p-values* = 0.000 < 0.05 so that H₂ is accepted. This shows that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua.

The third hypothesis (H₃) in this study states that compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Based on Table 5.14, it can be seen that the path coefficient value obtained has a positive value, namely 0.182 with *p-values* = 0.034 < 0.05 so that H₃ is accepted. This shows that compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua. The fourth hypothesis (H₄) in this study states that work facilities have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Based on Table 5.14, it can be seen that the path coefficient value obtained has a positive value, namely 0.097 with *p-values* = 0.011 < 0.05 so that H₄ is accepted. This shows that Work facilities have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua.

DISCUSSION

Based on the data analysis that has been done, this study found that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua. This means that the higher the motivation of employees to work, the more likely it is to encourage increased performance produced by employees. Employees who have high work enthusiasm tend to be motivated to work optimally so that they can achieve optimal performance as well. Referring to the *goal-setting theory*, it can be understood that goals that are specific, challenging, and accepted by individuals can improve performance because they can focus attention, encourage greater effort, increase perseverance, and encourage individuals to develop effective achievement strategies (Rohendi, 2016; Sarfraz et al., 2023). In relation to work motivation, employees who have high motivation tend to be more focused and enthusiastic in completing tasks that are directed at achieving certain goals (Eugénio et al., 2013). This is in line with the concept in *Goal Setting Theory*, where motivation that arises from clear and challenging goals will encourage individuals to show better performance. The positive relationship between work motivation and employee performance found in this study shows that when employees' psychological and professional needs are met through proper motivation, performance will naturally increase. Therefore, it is important for company management to continue to maintain and improve factors that can motivate employees, such as providing appreciation, guaranteeing job security, clarity of goals, and providing facilities that support work activities (Lau et al., 2021; Rubio-Mozos et al., 2020).

Based on the results of the questionnaire distribution, it can be seen that the disciplined behavior applied by employees, such as compliance with superiors' directions, implementation of established work procedures, and punctuality in attendance, plays an important role in encouraging optimal performance achievement (Nurhuda et al., 2019). Work discipline is the foundation for creating a structured, efficient, and professional work pattern. Employees who have a high level of discipline will be more focused in completing tasks, minimizing work errors, and being able to maintain consistent performance (Sihombing & Sitanggang, 2019). This condition greatly supports the achievement of work results that meet company expectations, indicated by accuracy in carrying out work, efficiency in producing output, and real contributions to improving work quality through providing constructive suggestions and initiatives. The positive relationship between work discipline and employee performance found in this study reflects that employees who are committed to work rules and ethics will be more responsible and results-oriented. A work environment that upholds discipline indirectly creates a productive and conducive work culture for individual and organizational growth (Hanif et al., 2012). Therefore, companies need to maintain and strengthen a culture of work discipline as a strategy to maintain and improve employee performance sustainably (Juniariani & Saputra, 2020).

Based on the results of the questionnaire distribution, it can be seen that the compensation system implemented at Galaxy Salon and Spa, such as fair salaries, performance-based incentives, and benefits in accordance with policies, plays an important role in encouraging employee morale and productivity. Compensation that is perceived as fair and appropriate provides motivational encouragement for employees to give their best performance (Darmawan et al., 2023). When employees feel that their efforts and contributions are financially appreciated, a sense of satisfaction, loyalty, and responsibility will emerge in carrying out their duties. This sense of satisfaction is then reflected in high performance, which is demonstrated through accuracy, efficiency, fulfillment of company expectations, and the initiative to provide suggestions for improvement. (Laksmi et al., 2024). In addition, a good compensation system also creates a conducive and healthy competitive work environment, where employees are motivated to continue to improve the quality of their work in order to receive awards for their achievements. This strengthens the relationship between compensation and performance, and encourages the creation of a productive and results-oriented work culture. Thus, it can be understood that compensation not only functions as a form of appreciation for hard work, but also as a strategic instrument in managing employee performance sustainably at Galaxy Salon and Spa.

Based on the results of the questionnaire distribution, it can be understood that adequate, comfortable, and easily accessible work facilities and infrastructure play an important role in supporting employee productivity and work effectiveness (Saputra, Darmawan, et al., 2024). Employees assess that the available inventory equipment is in optimal condition, the work environment is comfortable, and access to supporting facilities can support the implementation of daily tasks more efficiently and accurately. Good work facilities make it easier to complete work, reduce operational obstacles, and create a conducive work atmosphere (Laksmi & Saputra, 2024). This directly increases accuracy, efficiency, and work results that are in accordance with company expectations.

A comfortable physical work environment also has a positive impact on the psychological atmosphere of employees, so that they feel more motivated and focused on their work. Not only does it have an impact on work results, adequate work facilities also encourage employees to contribute more actively, such as by providing suggestions to improve work quality (Ferayanti et al., 2024). Overall, the results of this study confirm that good work facilities not only support smooth operations, but also increase work satisfaction and motivation, which ultimately leads to an increase in overall employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Pratiwi (2019) which states that work facilities have a positive and significant effect on employee performance where the more adequate the work facilities are, the more employee performance will increase. The results of this study are also in line with research conducted by Sari & Puspita (2023); Nurhadian (2021); Monalisa *et al.*, (2022); and Anandita *et al.*, (2021) who found that work facilities have a significant positive effect on employee performance. This indicates that the provision of good work facilities can improve employee performance optimally.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and discussions that have been described in the previous chapter regarding the influence of work motivation, work discipline, compensation, and work facilities on employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua. This means that the higher the employee motivation to work tends to encourage increased performance produced by employees.
2. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua. This means that the higher the employee's work discipline tends to encourage increased performance produced by employees.
3. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua. This means that the better the compensation given to employees, the more it will play a role in increasing employee job satisfaction which will have an impact on increasing employee performance.

Work facilities have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Galaxy Salon and Spa Jalan Taman Giri Nusa Dua. This means that the more adequate the work facilities that support employee work tend to help employees in creating optimal performance.

REFERENCES

1. Abdou, A. H., Hassan, T. H., & Moustafa, M. (2020). A Description of Green Hotel Practices and Their Role in Achieving Sustainable Development. *Sustainability*, 12, 1–20. <https://doi.org/doi:10.3390/su12229624>
2. Anggreni, N. K. D. A., Sara, I. M., & Saputra, K. A. K. (2023). The Effect of Sustainability Accounting, Work Environment, and Leadership on Employee Performance. *Journal of Entrepreneurial and Business Diversity*, 1(1), 72–77. <https://doi.org/10.38142/jebd.v1i1.73>
3. Apri Dahlius, & Ibrahim, M. (2016). Pengaruh Fasilitas Kerja Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Pada Pt. Bank RiauKepri Cabang Teluk Kuantan Kabupaten Kuantan Singingi Oleh: *JOM FISIP*, 3(2), 13–22.
4. Bohdanowicz, P., & Martinac, I. (2007). Determinants and benchmarking of resource consumption in hotels-Case study of Hilton International and Scandic in Europe. *Energy and Buildings*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2006.05.005>
5. Darmawan, N. A. S., Laksmi, P. A. S., & Saputra, K. A. K. (2023). Socialization of E-commerce for Marketing Agricultural Products in Sangsit Village, Sawan District, Buleleng Regency, Bali. *Community Service: Sustainability Development*, 1(1), 2018–2022.
6. Eugénio, T. P., Costa Lourenço, I., & Morais, A. I. (2013). Sustainability strategies of the company TimorL: extending the applicability of legitimacy theory. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 24(5), 570–582. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-03-2011-0017>
7. FERAYANTI, K. D., WAHYUNI, N. M., & LAKSMI, P. A. S. (2024). Customer Satisfaction As A Mediator For The Influencer And Word Of Mouth On Online Purchase Decisions For Fashion Products In Denpasar City. *Journal of Tourism, Economics and Policy*, 4(2), 151–156.
8. Hanif, M., Rizal, A., & Ratnawati, I. (2012). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi dan Kepuasan Kerja terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Studi Pada Rumah Sakit Panti Wilasa ‘Citarum’ Kota Semarang). *Diponegoro Journal of Management*, 1(2), 181–188.
9. Harris, L. L., Jackson, S. B., Owens, J., Seybert, N., & Jackson, S. B. (2021). Recruiting Dark Personalities for Earnings Management. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 0123456789. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-021-04761-z>
10. Juniariani, N. M. R., & Saputra, K. A. K. (2020). Internal Locus of Control dan Efek Computer Anxiety pada Kinerja Karyawan Keuangan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi*, 5(1), 45. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jia.v5i1.22668>
11. Ketchen, D. J. (2013). A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling. In *Long Range Planning* (Vol. 46, Issues 1–2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2013.01.002>
12. Laksmi, P. A. S., & Saputra, K. A. K. (2024). *Manajemen Pariwisata Budaya*. https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/PARIWISATA_BUDAYA/v3jNDwAAQBAJ?hl=id&gbpv=0
13. Laksmi, P. A. S., Selamet, I. K., Mangku, I. G. P., Saputra, K. A. K., Rashid, W. E. W., & Saihani, S. B. (2024). Management Strategy Planning And Implementation Of Advanced Technology In Increasing Agricultural Productivity. *RJOAS: Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*, 9(153), 97–106.
14. Lau, C., Tang, I. L. F., & Chan, W. (2021). Waterfront hotels' chillers: Energy benchmarking and esg reporting. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13116242>
15. Martela, F., Hankonen, N., Ryan, R. M., & Vansteenkiste, M. (2021). Motivating voluntary compliance to behavioural restrictions: Self-determination theory–based checklist of principles for COVID-19 and other emergency communications. *European Review of Social Psychology*, 32(2), 305–347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10463283.2020.1857082>
16. Merli, R., Preziosi, M., Acampora, A., & Ali, F. (2019). Why should hotels go green? Insights from guests experience in green hotels. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 81(May), 169–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2019.04.022>

17. Muisyo, P. K., Qin, S., Ho, T. H., & Julius, M. M. (2022). The effect of green HRM practices on green competitive advantage of manufacturing firms. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 33(1), 22–40. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMTM-10-2020-0388>
18. Nurhuda, A., Sardjono, S., & Purnamasari, W. (2019). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional, Disiplin Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Motivasi Dan Kinerja Karyawan Rumah Sakit Anwar Medika Jl. Raya Bypass Krian Km. 33 Balongbendo – Sidoarjo. *IQTISHADequity Jurnal MANAJEMEN*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.51804/iej.v1i1.355>
19. Praditya, R. A. (2022). Kinerja Organisasi Pada Manajemen Rantai Pasokan Pariwisata: Bagaimana Peran Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Kepuasan Pelanggan? *International Journal of Social, Policy and Law*, 3(2), 17–21.
20. Ragil Anandita, S., Indriyani, S., & Mahendri, W. (2021). Pengaruh Fasilitas Kerja Dan Komunikasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Studi Pada Cv. Zam - Zam Jombang). *Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Bung Hatta*, 16(2), 881–890. <https://doi.org/10.37301/jmubh.v16i2.19047>
21. Ramadhani, S. D. (2016). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Dan Motivasi Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Di Balai Pengembangan Kegiatan Belajar (Bpkb) Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta (Diy). *Jurnal Ilman*, 1–179.
22. Rohendi, S. N. & A. (2016). *Gaya kepemimpinan transformasional, budaya organisasi, dan kinerja karyawan dengan mediasi komitmen organisasi*. IV(1), 86–100.
23. Rubio-Mozos, E., García-Muiña, F. E., & Fuentes-Moraleda, L. (2020). Sustainable strategic management model for hotel companies: A multi-stakeholder proposal to “walk the talk” toward SDGS. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(20), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12208652>
24. Saputra, K. A. K. (2019). Case-Based Learning in Forensic Accounting Education. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Studies*, 1(6), 545–553. <https://doi.org/10.29103/ijevs.v1i6.1763>
25. Saputra, K. A. K., Darmawan, N. A. S., & Laksmi, P. A. S. (2024). *Kajian Etnografi Kinerja Berkelanjutan*.
26. Saputra, K. A. K., Laksmi, P. A. S., Suriani, N., & Ekajayanti, L. G. . S. (2024). Accounting Training to Support Transparent and Accountable Village Fund Reporting in Sibatana Village, KarangasemBali. *Community Service: Sustainability Development*, 1(2), 24–30.
27. Saputra, K. A. K., Subroto, B., Rahman, A. F., & Saraswati, E. (2023). Mediation Role of Environmental Management Accounting on the Effect of Green Competitive Advantage on Sustainable Performance. *Journal of Sustainability Science and Management*, 18(2), 103–115. <https://doi.org/10.46754/jssm.2023.02.008>
28. Sara, I. M., Saputra, K. A. K., & Utama, I. W. K. J. (2021). The Effects of Strategic Planning, Human Resource and Asset Management on Economic Productivity: A Case Study in Indonesia. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(4), 381–389. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no4.0381>
29. Sarfraz, M., Ozturk, I., Yoo, S., Raza, M. A., & Han, H. (2023). Toward a new understanding of environmental and financial performance through corporate social responsibility, green innovation, and sustainable development. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01799-4>
30. Sari, I. A. W. P., Dharmanegara, I. B. A., & Martadiani, A. A. M. (2023). The Influence Of Organizational Communication And Organizational Commitment On Employee Performance With Job Satisfaction As A Mediation Variable (Study On Employees Of Kinik Network PT. BHAKSENA). *International Journal of Environmental, Sustainability and Social Science*, 5(1), 194–208.
31. Sihombing, S., & Sitanggang, D. (2019). Organizational Citizenship Behavior Ditinjau Dari Kepuasan Kerja. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi & Keuangan*, 5(2), 191–208. <https://doi.org/10.54367/jrak.v5i2.533>
32. Sujana, E., & Saputra, K. A. K. (2020). Fraud detection and prevention methods: Inspector’s auditor’s perception in Bali. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(4), 8–16. <https://doi.org/10.5373/JARDCS/V12I4/20201413>
33. Taylor, Z. (2019). Pathways to legitimacy. *Planning Theory*, 18(2), 214–236. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1473095218806929>
34. Wang, H., Khan, M. A. S., Anwar, F., Shahzad, F., Adu, D., & Murad, M. (2021). Green Innovation Practices and Its Impacts on Environmental and Organizational Performance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11(January), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.553625>
35. Yin, Y., Wang, Y., & Lu, Y. (2019). Why firms adopt empowerment practices and how such practices affect firm performance? A transaction cost-exchange perspective. *Human Resource Management Review*, 29(1), 111–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2018.01.002>
36. Zhu, C., Wu, D. C. W., Hall, C. M., Fong, L. H. N., Koupaie, S. N., & Lin, F. (2023). Exploring non-immersive virtual reality experiences in tourism: Empirical evidence from a world heritage site. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 25(3), 372–383. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jtr.2574>